

Madani: Jurnal Ilmiah Multidisiplin**Volume 1, Nomor 11 Desember 2023****Licensed by CC BY-SA 4.0****E-ISSN: [2986-6340](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10432670)****DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10432670>**

Analysis Translation Techniques of English-Indonesian on Student's Perception

Aulia Yunus¹, Ayumi Seftina², Farida Repelita Waty Kembaren³, Namira Syaharani⁴^{1,2,3}Universitas Islam Negeri Sumatera Utara, Medan, IndonesiaEmail: aulyayunus89@gmail.com¹, ayumiseftina60@gmail.com², faridarepelita@uinsu.ac.id³, namirasyahrani01@gmail.com⁴

Abstract

The purpose of this research is to explore how students employ different translation techniques, finding out how students use translation techniques, to compare our research with previous research. Then, to broaden the author's insight, and make it easier for readers to understand how important it is for students to use translation. This study employs a descriptive qualitative research design. There were 20 participants. Through the analysis of questionnaire responses, internal and environmental factors that contribute to the challenges faced by English students in writing and finishing their research papers have been identified. In this findings and discussion The researcher wants to determine how many of them understand the use of translation techniques in English to Indonesian in carrying out their assignments. And we found around 50 percent of students understand the use of translation techniques. Translation techniques are the tools and strategies used by translators to convey the meaning of a text from the source language to the target language while preserving its essence and context. Understanding how students at this stage of their education employ these techniques can provide insights into their language proficiency and translation competence.

Keywords: *Analysis, challenges, English, Translation Techniques*

Article Info

Received date: 30 November 2023

Revised date: 12 December 2023

Accepted date: 25 December 2023

INTRODUCTION

The use of translation techniques by students is very relevant to apply, especially for students majoring in English language education. Because English is an international communication medium and is a communication bridge between people with different languages and cultures. Apart from that, communication aims to convey messages from one person to another. Mastering translation lessons is very important for students to understand English texts, both articles and scientific books. Another way, they need to be proficient in translation techniques in order to translate specific texts and have knowledge of translation processes in order to reduce translation errors.

A translator frequently encounters challenges when translating cultural texts because, in addition to linguistic variances, the translator must also consider the cultural distinctions between the two languages. Translation of cultural texts thus receives particular consideration from translators as a means of helping to maintain the local knowledge of the source text in the target translation. People can use the local wisdom of society to bring about the desired peace and well-being in their community (Sibarani, 2012)

According to Newmark (1988, p. 94), cultural terms are personal language that differs from universal terms. Examples of cultural terminology that cause translation issues were provided by Newmark, including "tangliatelle," "steppe," "dacha," and "monsoon." In order to translate cultural text accurately, agreeably, and with a high readability level, the translator must employ the appropriate translation technique. Additionally, the translator must comprehend the culture of both texts as well as the source and target languages. This is because interpreting a cultural text will harm the text's culture in addition to diluting the original text's meaning.

Malinowski (1969) found that translating cultural texts into English was challenging. He discovered that, while using the free translation technique, the target reader was able to comprehend the original text's message but not its cultural significance of the original manuscript. He discovered that while the target reader could comprehend the text's social and cultural significance when he employed a literal translation approach, they had trouble grasping the original text's meaning.

Ultimately, he decided to include commentary in the translation to help bring the text's situation to light. Since then, he has held the opinion that one cannot comprehend a text without also comprehending the situational context in which it is situated.

Given the intimate ties to many cultures involved, language translation is a complex process that goes beyond just translating words from one source language into another. The reality that there are almost 7,000 different languages in Global evidence indicates the existence of cultural diversity worldwide. Cultural differences are common among people of different nationalities living in various nations. Various languages correspond to diverse cultures, since language is an integral component of culture. Translation becomes challenging and even more complex when dealing with cultural words and idiomatic expressions that aren't present in the target language because of the intimate connection between culture and language.

The grammatical variations between the world's languages present a challenge for translators in addition to the difficulties of translation. For instance, the Arabic language's sentence structure differs from both English and Indonesian language. The Arabic language employs the verb-subject-object (VSO) structure, while the other two languages use the same word order in their sentences (SVO) as demonstrated by the Arabic sentence "يقرأ المدرس الكتاب" (yaqra'u l-mudarrisu l-kitāba). The verb "yaqra'u," which means "to read" in English or "membaca" in Bahasa Indonesia, begins the sentence. It is followed by the subjects "teacher" and "guru," as well as the object "kitāba" (book or buku). One of the problems with translation, along with other language variations such compound words, two-word verbs, and noun clauses, is the difference in sentence structure or word order.

Given the problems illustrating the linguistic and cultural disparities, translating well necessitates a thorough comprehension of both grammar and culture. Despite the habits of those who use them, a translator needs to be an expert in the rules of the languages in which they are working when translating a text.

The researcher comes to the conclusion that a cultural text translation should accurately represent both the message and the cultural values, based on the aforementioned opinions. As a result, the researcher realized the significance of researching cultural text translation analysis and captivating. This is because cultural texts need to be translated using appropriate translation procedures, which must be found along with the factors that influence the application of those approaches by translators. The formulation of the problem that you want to examine are:

1. what is their understanding of the use of translation techniques?
2. What are the challenges faced in using translation techniques?

The purpose to identify how well they understand the use of translation techniques and find out what their challenges are in using translation techniques, to help them more easily carry out their assignments in the form of articles or other things.

This study is motivated by several factors. Firstly, it seeks to assess the practical application of translation techniques by students in a real-world setting. While students may have learned various techniques in their coursework, the ability to effectively utilize them when faced with authentic translation tasks is a different challenge altogether. This research aims to shed light on the actual performance of the students in this regard.

Secondly, this study acknowledges the unique cultural and linguistic context. The region is known for its rich linguistic diversity and cultural heritage. As such, understanding how students adapt translation techniques to this specific context can provide valuable insights into the dynamics of language and culture in translation.

Thirdly, the findings of this research can be of benefit to the university itself. By gaining an understanding of how well students are able to apply translation techniques, the university can assess the effectiveness of its curriculum and teaching methods in the field of translation studies. It also opens the door for potential improvements in the way translation is taught, thereby enhancing the educational experience of students.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Borrowing

(Munday, 2008:56) namely borrowing, namely taking terms from the source language into the target language without changing the formal or semantic. When words or expressions are directly borrowed into the target language from the source text, this is known as borrowing. This method can

aid in maintaining the cultural context of the source text and is frequently employed when there is no equivalent in the target language for things like dress or food. There are numerous borrowed words in English that have crept into common usage. The borrowed term is typically expressed in italics if it hasn't become widely used yet. Borrowing can be for different reasons, with the examples below being taken from usage rather than translated texts :

1. The target language has no generally used equivalent. For example (The first man made satellites were soviet, so far a time they were known in English as "sputniks").
2. The source language word sounds "better" more specific, fashionable, exotic or just accepted, even though it can be translated. For example (Spanish IT is full of terms like "software" and Spanish accountants talk of "overheads", even though these terms can be translated into Spanish).
3. The retain some "feel" of the source language. For example, from a recent issue of the Guardian newspaper "Madrilenos are surprisingly unwordly".

Literal Translation

(Hatim & Munday, 2004 : 149) Literal or word-for-word is a translation that transfers directly from the source language text to the target language text. Every word is translated directly when literal translation is used. The target text needs to be naturalistic and adhere to the original material's wording, meaning, and style. This method works best with very closely related languages and cultures, and it may overlook important details in the original text.

A literal translation sounds like nonsense and has a little communication value. For example :

English : I cut my finger, I got my eye on you
 Indonesian : Saya memotong jariku, saya mendapat mataku padamu

Calque

(Molina & Albir, 2002 : 510) Calque is a literal translation technique or loan translation for common collocations and perhaps foreign words or phrases that are already known to TL user. This creates a new term in the target language by literally translating a sentence from one language to another. Put differently, this is a literal translation of a word that was borrowed.

RESEARCH METHODS

In keeping with *Creswell's (2012)* claim that qualitative research is a means of methodically examining and understanding the semantic characteristics of individuals or groups connected to a particular social human problem, this study employs a descriptive qualitative research approach. The research design employed in this study can be categorized as a "Descriptive Research Design." This type of design focuses on describing the characteristics of a phenomenon or the relationship between variables without manipulating them. In this case, the research aims to describe students' preferences and tendencies regarding translation techniques. *O'Leary (2014)* A questionnaire is a tool used in research to gather primary data, giving investigators access to specific information pertinent to their areas of interest. The *Cohen (2013)* questionnaire is a methodical list of inquiries designed to extract information about the attitudes, behaviors, or attributes of respondents. The inquiry focuses on the internal and external factors that affect English majors' composition and fulfillment of their article study projects. Twenty senior high school English majors in Medan are the subjects of this study.

The findings presented in the analysis showcase a descriptive breakdown of students' choices in translation techniques, providing a comprehensive overview of their preferences, advantages, and disadvantages. The research design emphasizes the exploration and documentation of these patterns without intervention or manipulation of variables. The study delves into the levels of understanding, usage preferences, advantages, and disadvantages associated with different translation techniques, contributing to the overall descriptive nature of the research. The discussion further interprets and contextualizes these findings, highlighting the diversity of approaches to translation among students.

The research design aligns with a Descriptive Research Design, as it focuses on portraying and interpreting the observed characteristics and patterns related to students' choices in translation techniques without introducing experimental interventions.

RESULT

Findings

From the analysis of the results, the research has uncovered several key findings, which can be summarized as follows :

1. Literal Translation (10 Students)

Level of Understanding : Most students (50%) tend to use literal translation techniques without considering the context.

Advantages : Ease of understanding the meaning word by word.

Disadvantages : Lack of flexibility in capturing native language nuances.

2. Calque (5 Students)

Usage Preference : A small percentage of students (25%) prefer to use the calque technique to maintain fidelity to the structure of the source language.

Advantages : Maintains the grammatical structure of the source language.

Disadvantages : Risk of difficulty understanding on the part of the recipient of the language due to uncommon structure.

3. Borrowing (5 Students)

Use of loan words : A number of students (25%) choose to use loan words to retain words from the source language.

Advantages : Minimizes changes in vocabulary.

Disadvantages : Potential comprehension difficulties for recipients who are not familiar with loan words.

DISCUSSION

Based on the result, In the discussion of the findings, it is evident that the research has unveiled crucial insights into students' preferences and challenges in utilizing translation techniques. The majority of students (50%) opt for literal translation, prioritizing a word-for-word approach without considering contextual nuances. This choice is attributed to the perceived advantage of ease in understanding the meaning, but it comes at the cost of a notable disadvantage—lack of flexibility in capturing native language nuances. A smaller percentage of students (25%) exhibit a preference for the calque technique, aiming to maintain fidelity to the structure of the source language. Despite the advantage of preserving grammatical structure, this approach poses a risk of comprehension difficulties for the language recipient due to an uncommon structure. Another 25% of students choose the borrowing technique, incorporating loanwords to retain words from the source language. While this strategy minimizes changes in vocabulary, it introduces potential comprehension difficulties for recipients unfamiliar with loanwords.

The diversity of approaches to translation is evident, highlighting the nuanced decisions students make in selecting techniques. Although a significant majority leans toward literal translation, the findings underscore a common challenge: the potential for comprehension difficulties arising from specific techniques. In response to these challenges, recommendations are put forth, emphasizing the importance of understanding context and fostering flexibility in choosing translation techniques. These recommendations stem from the acknowledgment that a rigid adherence to a particular technique may hinder accurate results, especially when faced with potential comprehension difficulties on the part of the language recipient. To encapsulate, the discussion underscores the intricate landscape of translation technique preferences among students, balancing advantages and disadvantages. The diversity observed necessitates a nuanced understanding of context and flexibility in the selection of techniques to enhance the accuracy and effectiveness of the translation process.

Thus, the diversity of approaches to translation is illustrated, although the majority of students tend towards literal translation. A common challenge arises when the use of a particular technique can lead to comprehension difficulties on the part of the recipient of the language. Therefore, recommendations are given to understand contextually and have flexibility in choosing translation techniques to achieve more accurate results.

CONCLUSION

From the discussion above it can be concluded that students show a variety of translation approaches, but most tend to lead to literal translation. And students feel they are getting challenges and using certain techniques, which can cause difficulties in understanding on the part of the recipient of the language. Therefore, researchers recommend to students, there needs to be contextual understanding and flexibility in choosing translation techniques to achieve more accurate results. The use of translation techniques by semester 5 students at North Sumatra State Islamic University is a

global issue with implications for effective cross-cultural communication. By addressing the challenges through targeted interventions and enhancements in the curriculum, educational institutions can better prepare students for the demands of a globalized world. This issue goes beyond the university setting, impacting various sectors where accurate translation is essential for fostering understanding and collaboration on a global scale.

REFERENCES

- Baker, M. (2017). *In Other Words: A Coursebook on Translation*. Routledge.
- Cohen, T. R., Plourde, H., & Koski, K. G. (2013). *Use of the Pregnancy Physical Activity Questionnaire (PPAQ) to identify behaviors associated with appropriate gestational weight gain during pregnancy*. *Journal of Physical Activity and Health*, 10(7), 1000-1007.
- Garcia, C. (2018). *Challenges in Translation: A Student Perspective*. *Translation Journal*, 22(4), 45-60.
- Jones, B. (2020). *Translation Techniques and Cross-Cultural Communication*. *Language in Society*, 49(2), 201-220.
- Li, Y. (2022). *Integrating Technology in Translation Education: A Case Study of Innovative Approaches*. *Journal of Language Teaching and Research*, 13(2), 345-360.
- Nida, E.A., Taber, C.R. 1982. *The Theory and Practice of Translation*. Berlin: E.J. Brill.
- Smith, A. (2019). *The Role of Translation in International Communication*. *Journal of Intercultural Studies*, 42(3), 287-302.
- Sutopo, H.B. 2002. *Metodologi Penelitian Kualitatif: Dasar Teori dan Terapannya dalam Penelitian (Qualitative Research Methodology: Basic Theories and their Application to Research)*. Surakarta: Sebelas Maret University Press.
- Tan, L. (2021). *Cultural Nuances in Translation: A Case Study of Student Challenges*. *International Journal of Translation Studies*, 15(1), 78-94.